

Privacy requirements elicitation: A systematic literature review and perception analysis of IT practitioners

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Abstract Context: During the software development process and throughout the software lifecycle, organizations must guarantee users' privacy by protecting personal data. There are several studies in the literature proposing methodologies, techniques, and tools for privacy requirements elicitation. These studies report that practitioners must use systematic approaches to specify these requirements during initial software development activities to avoid users' data privacy breaches. **Objective:** The main goal of this study is to identify which methodologies, techniques, and tools are used in privacy requirements elicitation in the literature. We have also investigated Information Technology (IT) practitioners' perceptions regarding the methodologies, techniques, and tools identified in the literature. **Method:** We have carried out a systematic literature review (SLR) to identify the methodologies, techniques, and tools used for privacy requirements elicitation. Besides, we have surveyed IT practitioners to understand their perception of using these techniques and tools in the software development process. **Results:** We have found several methodologies, techniques, and tools proposed in the literature to carry out privacy requirements elicitation. Out of 78 studies cataloged within the SLR, most of them did not verify their methodologies and techniques in a practical case study or illustrative contexts (38 studies), and less than 35% of them (26 studies) experimented with their propositions within an industry context. The Privacy Safeguard method (PriS) is the best known among the 198 practitioners in the industry who participated in the survey. Moreover, use cases and user story are their most-used techniques. **Conclusion:** This qualitative study shows a perception of IT practitioners different from that presented in other research papers, and suggests that methodologies, techniques, and tools play an important role in IT practitioners' perceptions about privacy requirements elicitation.

Address(es) of author(s) should be given

Keywords Privacy Requirements Elicitation · Systematic Literature Review · Methodologies · Techniques · Tools

1 Selected Primary Studies

ID	Reference	Methodologies	Techniques	Tools
S1	Yu and Cysneiros [79]	i* Model; Non-Functional Requirements (NFR) Framework.		
S2	He et al. [27]	Discretionary and Mandatory Access Controls (DAC and MAC); Privacy-Aware Role-Based Access Control (PARBAC).		Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realizable, and Traceable (SMaRT).
S3	Liu et al. [41]	i* Model; Agent-Based Model; Alloy Language; Agent-Oriented Modeling Framework.		
S4	Jensen et al. [31]	Goal-Oriented Approach.		STRuctured Analysis for Privacy (STRAP) Tool.
S5	Sindre and Opdahl [70]		Misuse Case.	
S6	Mouratidis and Giorgini [48]	i* Model; Secure Tropos.		T-Tool.
S7	Kalloniatis et al. [33]	Privacy Safeguard Method (PriS).		
S8	Tøndel et al. [73]	NFR Framework.	Misuse Case; Use case.	
S9	Miyazaki et al. [46]	Development Life Cycle Models and Cost.	Questionnaire; Use Case; Flow Charts.	Privacy Requirements Elicitation Technique (PRET) Tool.

S10	Kalloniatis et al. [34]	PriS Conceptual Framework.		
S11	Kalloniatis et al. [35]	Goal Model; Directed Acyclic Graph.		PriS Tool.
S12	Bijwe and Mead [11]	Goal-Based Requirements Analysis Method (GBRAM); Pattern-Based Approach (PBA); E-Commerce Personalization Approach (ECPA); Soft Systems Methodology (SSM); Feature-Oriented Domain Analysis (FODA).	Use Case; Misuse Case; Attack Trees; User-Role Hierarchies (URH); System Architecture Diagrams (SAD); Interviews.	PRET Tool.
S13	Islam et al. [30]	Secure Tropos; Goal Driven Security Risk Management (GSRM).		
S14	Deng et al. [16]	Linkability, Identifiability, Non-repudiation, Detectability, Information Disclosure, Content Unawareness and Policy/Consent Non-compliance (LIND-DUN).	Data Flow Diagrams (DFD); Use Case.	
S15	Kalloniatis et al. [36]	Pris Extension.		Pris Tool.

S16	Mead et al. [45]	<p>PRET; Security Quality Requirements Engineering (SQUARE); Soft Systems Methodology (SSM); Quality Function Deployment (QFD); Controlled Requirements Expression (CORE); Issue-Based Information Systems (IBIS); FODA; Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA); Accelerated Requirements Method (ARM); Reusable Legal Requirements; GBRAM; PBA; ECPA.</p>	<p>Misuse Case; Joint Application Development (JAD); Questionnaire.</p>	
S17	Mouratidis et al. [49]	<p>NFR Framework; i* Model; Secure Tropos; Keep All Objectives Satisfied (KAOS); Goal-Based Requirements Analysis Method (GBRAM); Role Based Access Control (RBAC); Moffett-Nuseibeh (M-N) Framework; STRuctured Analysis for Privacy (STRAP); Privacy Safeguard (PriS).</p>		
S18	Beckers [10]	<p>Conceptual Framework for Security Requirements Engineering (CF); PriS; LINDDUN; Privacy-Friendly System Design from Spiekermann (FPRSD).</p>		

S19	Neureiter et al. [53]	Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS); Privacy-RAMS; LINDDUN.		
S20	Kalloniatis et al. [37]	Secure Tropos; Pris.		
S21	Amorim et al. [5]	Privacy by Design; Digital Image Analysis (DIA).		
S22	Radics et al. [65]	Poolsappasit and Ray's Framework; Sensor-Safe and MAPaS framework; Beckers' Method; LINDDUN; PriS; Model by Hong; Privacy Requirements Engineering Process (PREPProcess).		
S23	Martín et al. [43]	Privacy by Design; Privacy Enhancing Technology (PET), Pris; i* Model.		OASIS-Privacy Management Reference Model Methodology (PMRM) Tools.
S24	Breaux et al. [12]		Survey; Interview; DFD.	
S25	Ganji et al. [21]	NFR Framework; i* Model; Secure Tropos; KAOS; GBRAM; RBAC; M-N Framework, Bellotti-Sellen Framework, STRAP; PriS, Caprice, SecuriTas, Easy Win-Win.		
S26	Notario et al. [54]	Goal-Oriented; System Analysis Approach; Privacy by Design.		

S27	Gharib et al. [24]		Questionnaire; Scenario.	
S28	Argyropoulos et al. [7]	Secure Tropos Approach; Secure Tropos.	Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN).	
S29	Mukisa and Rashid [51]	LINDDUN.		
S30	Pattakou et al. [55]	SQUARE; Model Oriented Security Requirements Engineering (MOSRE); Security Requirements Engineering Framework (SREF); Security Requirements Engineering Process (SREP); Secure Tropos; KAOS; Problem-based Security Requirements Elicitation (Pressure); LINDDUN; SQUARE; PriS.	BPMN.	
S31	Diamantopoulou et al. [17]	Secure Tropos Graphical Notation.		
S32	Gharib et al. [25]	Privacy by Design.	Unified Modeling Language (UML) Diagram.	
S33	Gharib and Mylopoulos [23]	COPri - a Core Ontology for Privacy Requirements Engineering.	BPMN.	
S34	Herwanto et al. [29]		User Story.	
S35	Junior et al. [32]		Questionnaire; Personas; User Story.	
S36	Pattakou et al. [56]	LINDDUN; SQUARE; PriS; RBAC; STRAP; Secure Tropos; PriS; i* Model; PRET.		PriS Tool.

S37	da Silva et al. [69]	Design of Crowdsourcing.		
S38	Mai et al. [42]	Natural Language Processing; Gamification.	Use Case; UML Diagram.	Restricted Misuse Case Modeling - Verifier (RMCM-V) Tool.
S39	Ayala-Rivera and Pasquale [8]	Business Analysis Body of Knowledge (BABOK).	Use Case; Questionnaire.	SMART Tool.
S40	Levy and Hadar [39]	Design Thinking.	Empathy Map.	
S41	Coles et al. [15]	Process Based on Computer Aided Integration of Requirements and Information Security (CAIRIS).	Use case; Personas; UML Diagrams; DFD; Semi-Structured Interview.	Tool Supported Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).
S42	Peixoto and Silva [59]	Goal-Oriented Modeling Language.	UML Diagram; Survey.	

S43	Lim et al. [40]		Interview; Questionnaire; Brainstorming; Prototype; Use Case; Workshop; Affinity Mapping; Crowdsourcing Survey; Data Mining; Content Analysis; Cultural Probe; Ethnographic Data; Focal Group; Scenario; Roles; Service Blueprint.	
S44	Peixoto et al. [57]	Privacy Criteria Method (PCM).	User Story.	PCM Tool.
S45	Netto et al. [52]		Interview; Case Study; Focus Group.	
S46	García-Mireles et al. [22]	PriS Method; Privacy by Design; LIND-DUN; General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).		
S47	Mohammadi et al. [47]	ISO/IEC 29100; GDPR; SPARQL, a query language for triple stores.		
S48	Veseli et al. [77]	Framework LIND-DUN.	DFD.	
S49	Rösch et al. [66]	GDPR.		
S50	Bartolini et al. [9]	Conceptual Model of GDPR-Focused User Stories.	User Story.	

S51	Pullonen et al. [64]	Privacy-Oriented Goals; Privacy-Enhanced BPMN (PE-BPMN).	BPMN.	
S52	Stach and Steimle [71]	Recommender-Based Privacy Requirements Elicitation (EPICUREAN) and Privacy System for Internet of Things Applications (PATRON); Privacy by Design.	Interviews; Modeling and Data Mining Techniques.	
S53	Tsohou et al. [75]		Questionnaire; Interview.	
S54	Toots et al. [74]		BPMN.	
S55	Ahmadian et al. [2]		UML Diagram.	
S56	Vilela et al. [78]	System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA); i* Model.		
S57	Mavroeidi et al. [44]	GDPR.	UML Diagram.	
S58	Peixoto et al. [60]	Privacy criteria Method.	Interview.	
S59	Ehécatl Morales-Trujillo et al. [18]	Privacy by Design; GDPR.		
S60	Ferraris and Gago [19]	JSON-Based Requirement Elicitation; Security, Availability, Privacy, Identity and Safety (TrUStAPIS); K-Model proposed in previous work Ferraris et al. [20].		
S61	Mouratidis et al. [50]	Cloud Security Analysis; Security Mitigation Analysis and Transparency Analysis; SectroCloud Module.		

S62	Perera et al. [62]	Set of Guidelines Generated by the Adequacy of Privacy by Design for the Context of Internet Of Things.		
S63	Peixoto [58]	PCM.	User Story.	PCM Tool.
S64	Salnitri et al. [67]	Security, Privacy and Trust Approach (SePTA); Goal-Based Modelling Languages; Socio-Technical Security Modelling Language (STS-ml) Diagram; Secure Tropos; i* Model.	BPMN.	STS-Tool and SecTro Tool.
S65	Carvalho et al. [14]	i* Model.	Survey; Questionnaire.	
S66	Peixoto et al. [61]	iStar; Secure Tropos; Problem Frames; NFR Framework; SI* Modelling; GRL; Threat Model; KAOS; SecBPMN-ml; UML4PF.	Use Case; DFD.	
S67	Ahmadian [1]	Model-Based Privacy by Design; Model-Based Cost Estimation; PET; RAMS; CARiSMA.	UML Diagram.	
S68	Canedo et al. [13]		User Story; Use Case; Interview; BPMN.	
S69	He et al. [28]		Questionnaire.	Amazon Mechanical Turk.
S70	Tsohou et al. [76]	Privacy by Design; Secure Tropos.	Questionnaire; Interview; User Story.	SecTro Tool.
S71	Tomashchuk et al. [72]	GDPR; Chinese Cybersecurity Act.	Case Study; DFD.	
S72	Piras et al. [63]	Secure Tropos.	Questionnaire.	STS-Tool.
S73	Akil et al. [3]	GDPR.	Use Case.	

S74	Gharib et al. [26]	GDPR.	UML Diagram.	SPARQL Tool.
S75	Sangaroonilp et al. [68]	GDPR; ISO/IEC 29100.		
S76	Ansari et al. [6]	Security Threat Oriented Requirements Engineering (STORE); LIND-DUN.	Interview; Brainstorming; Questionnaire.	
S77	Alkubaisy et al. [4]	Secure Tropos Methodology; DEFeND Platform; ConfIS Framework.	Survey.	IDEMIX Tool; SecTro Tool.
S78	Kitsiou et al. [38]	Privacy by Design.	Questionnaire.	

Table 1: Selected Primary Studies from 2002 to 2021

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